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Abstract: *The Asian Fortress, Emerging From Isolation. A Belt, a Road, a Bank, China ramped up its territorial claims in the South China Sea, China has also bolstered its military cooperation with Russia, China’s Direct Challenges to America, A Bold Forecast, A Coming Trade War, has acquired real estate in many important ports and choke points, Why the Trumpet Watches China.*

Key words: *Economic and Political Miracles, The Asian Fortress, The Silk Road, Mao Zedong, Chinese-Soviet, Richard Nixon, Mikhail Gorbachev, Friendship Cooperation Agreement, Shanghai Cooperation Organization, Military Cooperation, Major Weapons Systems, Xi Jinping, General Flurry, Ezekiel, Prophecies, Yuan, Mr, Armstrong.*

It is one among the foremost impressive economic and political miracles in contemporary world. And it isn’t over yet. China could be a sovereign state with a population of over 1.3 billion people. the state possesses the world’s largest economy by some measurements, the world’s largest population and therefore the fourth-largest territory. These are the building blocks of a superpower. While the planet anticipates China gaining superpower status, analysts debate over when and whether its rise are peaceful. The Trumpet forecasts that China will still grow as a formidable power, combining its strength with Russia. Further, we forecast that it’ll play a significant role in waging economic war that may devastate America. The Asian Fortress, China is found in East Asia. Its east borders the Pacific. Its southeastern border is usually a hilly jungle difficult to travel through. The south and west of China border the Himalayas, the world’s tallest chain. This poses another barrier to trade and military forces, except on its northwestern border through Kazakhstan. The famous medieval network of trade routes from Europe to Asia, called the trade route, ran through Kazakhstan to China. To China’s north, the Gobi Desert runs along China’s border with Mongolia.

China also borders Russia to the north in an exceedingly relatively uninhabited region. With borders like these, China is geographically secure. Historically, its geography allowed China to develop without much interaction with foreign powers, unless it chose to. Its territory and population size also make

it hard to beat. the sole successful invasion of China was by the Mongolian horsemen within the 1200s. while the japanese invaded and occupied large parts of eastern China within the 1930s, they might never get the Chinese to capitulate.

The British Empire’s prosperous trade actually destabilized China. The rich coastal areas cashing in on the trade resisted government policies and control that sought to curb trade. This led to the collapse of the central government and warfare. it absolutely was during this context that Japan invaded and remarkably did not conquer. All of this shows that while China is prone to invasion from the coast, the important threat isn’t from a military invasion. No nation has the interest or the forces to invade and occupy Asian nation and hope to win. the 000 threat is economic. it's vital to China’s prosperity that no nation can threaten it economically through its coast.

Emerging From Isolation, The history that's important to the Trumpet’s forecasts begins in 1949 when revolutionary established the People’s Republic of China. Mao modeled China’s political structures on those of the Communist USSR. This attracted Soviet loans, boosted growth within the Chinese economy, and put it on an ideological path opposite of the u. s.. initially the connection between Russia and China was successful. The Soviet advisers and loans increased industrialization in a very backward agrarian society. Mao signed a mutual defense treaty with the state in February 1950 and declared that the Chinese-Soviet friendship would be “everlasting, indestructible and inalienable.” the connection began to interrupt down after Mao launched his own modernization program in 1958 that failed. His radical attempts to remake China’s society reversed many of the economic gains. Russia openly criticized China and discontinue military aid. Within 15 years, the friendship ended.

The Chinese began to drift from Soviet Russia both philosophically and strategically, and commenced looking elsewhere for economic prosperity. In 1971, the People’s Republic of China gained membership within the international organisation, raising its status to a serious world political power. the subsequent year, U.S. President United States President visited China, the primary step in formalizing relations between the 2 countries. The visit paved the way for the robust economic ties the 2 nations share today. it absolutely was within the 1970s that China’s economic process really began to require off. In December 1978, China allowed farmers to sell their produce in local markets, a step faraway from pure communism. the govt also allowed individual businesses to conduct trade with foreign businesses. From 1978 to 2012, China’s gross domestic product grew a mean of 9.4 percent each year. No other nation’s economy has grown so fast for therefore long. After 35 years of virtually uninterrupted growth, by some

measures, like purchasing power, China's economy is now the biggest within the world. China's per capita gross domestic product rose from \$439 in 1950 to \$7,578 in 2014. that's a stimulating achievement. Since opening up trade to foreign markets, China has abandoned its historic isolation.

The Trumpet also watches China's relationship with Russia, which has undergone dramatic changes. the link reached a coffee in 1969 when Russian and Chinese troops fought a border battle. But beginning in 1989, when Soviet President solon visited Beijing, China and Russia's relationship has strengthened. In 1991, the 2 countries resolved their border differences, and in 2001, they signed a "friendship cooperation agreement."

The two nations formed the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in 1996 to strengthen political and economic cooperation with Central Asian states. China is now Russia's largest trading partner, while Russia may be a valuable source of oil and fossil fuel for China. it's these two factors, China's increasing economic power and its strengthening relationship with Russia, that the Trumpet follows and both of those trends still grow. The question on analysts' minds is whether or not China's growth and ambition will still be peaceful, or if it'll intercommunicate war. China's recent actions provides a clear answer.

A Belt, a Road, a Bank. In recent years, China has been expanding its ties with the remainder of Asia. In 2013, China launched its "One Belt, One Road" strategy to create transportation infrastructure routes for trade from Asia to Africa and Europe. It covers a region that holds 55 percent of the world's gross national product, 70 percent of the worldwide population and 75 percent of known energy reserves.

In 2016, China launched the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, a replacement Chinese-run international bank. The bank reduces Asia's dependence on the U.S.-controlled IBRD and aims to switch the U.S. dollar with the Chinese Yuan in trade. When the bank was proposed in 2013, the U.S. tried to convince other nations to not join, but failed even to influence its closest allies. This handed the U.S. an embarrassing defeat and clearly signaled that China is aggressively looking to interchange the U.S. in certain markets. And Many Islands, The clearest indication that its challenge won't be peaceful comes from what China is doing militarily. In 2008, China became the world's second-largest military spender. it's been modernizing its navy and is ready to possess more ships than the U.S. Navy by 2020.

In 2014, China ramped up its territorial claims within the South China Sea when it began creating artificial islands in disputed waters and militarizing them. a number of the islands are as far as 800 miles from Asian country, but only 150 miles

from the Philippines. in line with international organization law and therefore the International Court for Arbitration’s 2016 ruling, such turf belongs to the Philippines. But China refuses to just accept the court’s ruling or law, and neither is enforced.

China has also bolstered its military cooperation with Russia. Since 2005, Russia and China have conducted joint military exercises. While Chinese troops haven’t been sent against the U.S, China is already attacking America through cyberwarfare.

China’s Direct Challenges to America. In 2013, China hacked and stole XXIV major weapons systems from the U.S. it had been one in every of the biggest breaches in U.S. military security. Since then, multiple high-profile hacks have targeted U.S. utility companies and American governing body. China also opened a brand new front in its challenge to the U.S. space warfare. In 2007, China shot a missile into space to destroy an old artificial satellite, proving it could threaten U.S. satellites. of these actions show China’s plans to challenge and eventually replace the U.S. as a superpower. A Bold Forecast, The Trumpet follows its parent magazine, the Plain Truth, by reporting and analyzing Chinese cooperation with Russia and its recent economic process. During a time when China was an undeveloped nation squabbling with Russia, Plain Truth editor in chief Herbert W. Armstrong forecast that China would soon become a strong nation that might rally behind Russia to counter threats from the West.

A December 1959 Plain Truth issue stated: Lenin wrote that the thanks to Paris, London and the big apple is via Beijing and Delhi. a part of the Communist plan is to position India and Pakistan in an exceedingly giant vice between Russia and China. China insists it's a right not only to Tibet but [also] to several parts of India and geographical area. Their constant dream for hundreds of years has been ultimate world conquest! China knows, however, that during this highly industrialized age she will accomplish this dream only as an ally of Russia. China is now able to begin devouring the remainder of Asia with Russia’s secret military backing. it's hard to think that in 1959 someone was warning that China would be a threat to the globe order which it might side with Russia to try to to so. But Mr. Armstrong did and he was right. China remains trying to realize its dream to become a world superpower. Current Chinese President Xi Jinping promised in his book The Governance of China that China will achieve this by 2049. And today it's all over again an ally of Russia. Since that forecast, Trumpet editor in chief Gerald Flurry has added more detail to how China will try to achieve its dream. And it's everything to try to to with the West and its standard of living.

A Coming Trade War, Gerald Flurry forecasts that China will aggressively seek to exchange the U.S., such a lot in order that it'll visit economic war. But it won't do so alone. In his booklet Ezekiel: The End-Time Prophet, Mr. Flurry writes: "Europe and Asia may go together to economically besiege America." Until recent disagreements put the U.S.-China relationship on shakier ground, this wasn't a well-liked view, because China and also the U.S. are so economically tied together. First, China holds over \$1.1 trillion in U.S. federal debt, making it one in all the biggest foreign holders of U.S. debt. A conflict between the 2 nations would see the worth of China's investment drop.

Second, trade between the 2 nations is big. Altogether, \$598 billion worth of products was traded between China and America in 2015. This made China America's third-biggest trade partner. America is China's second-largest trading partner after the eu Union. However, of these goods, the U.S. only exported \$116 billion worth while it imported \$482 billion worth from China. that's a deficit of \$366 billion, meaning China has more to lose if a conflict does erupt. That's nearly 1/2 the full U.S. deficit.

Prophecy is that the guide. it's why Mr. Armstrong was accurate in his forecasts and why Mr. Flurry is accurate in his. a 3rd of the Bible is prophecy and most of it's for our time today. Bible prophecy describes an economic siege on America and Britain that's orchestrated by the EU and China.

We forecast that the U.S. and British peoples are not noted within the cold as Europe and Asia cooperate and call the shots within the global economy. The U.S. are literally besieged, economically frozen out of world trade! Events are moving toward the fulfillment of this prophecy. In recent years, the EU's economic powerhouse overtook the U.S. and Japan to become China's biggest trading partner. China and Europe have undertaken many joint ventures in recent years, including a 2015 landmark deal between Germany's largest exchange and China's exchange Trade System a deal that's significantly strengthening financial links between the 2 sides. The Trumpet forecasts that the U.S. and British peoples are going to be omitted within the cold as Europe and Asia cooperate and call the shots within the global economy. The U.S. are going to be literally besieged, economically frozen out of world trade! This prophecy is additionally described in Deuteronomy 28, which foretells of America being besieged by its enemies: "And he shall besiege thee altogether thy gates, until thy high fenced walls come down, wherein thou trusted, throughout all thy land, which the Lord thy God hath given thee." Mr. Flurry writes about this passage: "For a few years, Mr. Armstrong said the siege prophesied in verse 52 symbolized America's economy being battered by foreign competition. 'And he shall besiege thee altogether thy gates.

These gates talk to strategic choke points in world trade. Over 90 percent of world trade is carried on the seas. These choke points are narrow shipping lanes through which much of world trade travels. In fact, quite 40 percent of the world’s oil supply passes through six relatively narrow shipping lanes. The choke points of world trade are strategic sea gates which will be accustomed pack up trade, like the Panama Canal, the Suez Canal, the Bab el-Mandeb at the southern entrance to the Red Sea, the Turkish Straits, Gibraltar, the Strait of Malacca by Singapore and also the Strait of Hormuz by Iran. China has acquired realty in many important ports and choke points. It bought Panama’s largest port and also the Pakistani port of Gwadar, near the Strait of Hormuz. It now controls the Australian port city of Darwin. Most of those gates were once controlled by the us and also the geographical area, but the tide has turned within the previous couple of decades. Mr. Flurry continues concerning these gates: Who has those gates? America and Britain have or had the gates, and that we are visiting be besieged all told of them. we've got already virtually lost control of all of them. this is often a prophecy for this end time.

The Holy empire, [a 10-nation European federation that may soon initiate of the EU] together with the kings of the east (the Asian nations), will cause economic problems and produce on destruction in some ways “until thy high and fenced walls come down, wherein thou trusted, throughout all thy land: and he shall besiege thee altogether thy gates throughout all thy land, which the Lord thy God hath given thee”. the important pressure is coming from without. “In all thy gates”

refers to a trade war.

[The Fiery Cross Reef in the South China Sea \(as shown here in the summers of 2014, 2015 and 2016\) was built to extend China’s military presence in disputed waters.](#)

[World trade is dependent upon the function of certain strategic sea gates: 1\) Panama Canal, 2\) Gibraltar, 3\) Turkish Straits, 4\) Suez Canal, 5\) Bab](#)

[el-Mandeb, 6\) Strait of Hormuz, 7\) Strait of Malacca](#)

Because of these prophecies, the Trumpet watches China as it acquires more ports and continues to challenge America economically. For much of China's history it was an isolationist regional power. But now, thanks to Soviet and American help, China is a world heavyweight. And in order to protect itself and to secure its economic needs, it will act aggressively.

These prophecies go beyond a currency war or a loss of manufacturing jobs. They foretell an all-out economic war that will destroy America's economy! Imagine what would happen if China unloaded all its holdings of U.S. debt. Imagine what would happen to America's standard of living if cheap Chinese goods were no longer sold. Imagine what would happen to U.S. trade if ports and sea gates were closed off. China will be one of the leading nations to bring these scenarios to fruition.

Why the Trumpet Watches China, It is amazing to see how God's prophecies about China for our day coincide with China's recent activity. God gave China its unique geography and influenced world events enough to ensure they would unfold according to His prophecies. Now this Asian giant is coming out of its isolationist ways. It has gained tremendous economic clout that poses a considerable threat to the United States. Its capability as a military power is also rising to levels commensurate with those foretold in Scripture.

But that doesn't get to the heart of why the Trumpet reports on China's rise. We follow this trend because of what will happen after the siege. All of these major events prophesied in the Bible are part of a series of events that lead right up to the return of Jesus Christ. So when the Trumpet reports on these disturbing trends, it's with the anticipation and hope of what they ultimately lead to: a better world, led by the only government capable of bringing peace.

Should you fear China:

Over the last 60 years, China has transformed from a poor, struggling nation to an economic juggernaut. Most analysts say that the 21st century will belong to China. How strong will the Chinese get? And will they affect your life?

The Bible actually describes the economic might of 21st-century China and specifically prophesies the trade bloc that is developing between Asia and Europe . Moreover, it prophesies that China and its Asian allies will use their economic power to field a 200 million-man army and go to war. To learn what the Bible says about modern China.

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